

REQUIREMENTS FOR STRENGTHENING GOVERNANCE IN THE YEMENI AND ARAB HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY

Abdul Razzaq Abdullah Al-Mahbashi

Public Administration Development Center, Sana'a University, Sana'a, Yemen.
Email: almhbshybdalrzaq1@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study aimed to identify the requirements for strengthening governance in Yemeni and Arabic higher education institutions. The study used a descriptive approach and a content analysis of 25 previous studies on this research topic. The paper revealed several important results. First and most importantly, the governance aspects in the Yemeni and Arab universities are characterized by deficiency and shortcomings. Second, the paper revealed the necessity of working to develop the Yemeni and Arabic university governance by adopting a group of values, the most prominent of which are rational leadership, seriousness, commitment, participation, transparency, accountability, justice, integrity, creativity, innovation, invention, total quality, globalization, academic freedom and sustainable development. Thirdly, strategic goals and a number of initiatives and procedures, including the adoption and dissemination of principles of governance by the Yemeni and Arab universities, building alliances among Arab universities to establish a general framework common to practice governance and achieving sustainable development through governance application should be set up. Based on the findings, the paper proposes a number of useful recommendations related to the research topic.

Keywords: Governance, Yemeni Universities, Arab Universities, Higher Education Institutions.

INTRODUCTION

Countries seek to develop their universities and educational institutions out of their belief in the importance of continuous review and permanent development that takes into account the changes of the era and the requirements of society as well as the requirements of development towards the desired knowledge society. This is usually achieved by means of review and evaluation of educational institutions in an attempt to look to the future and develop a strategy that determines the path and provides multiple options for education, and is able to set priorities.

There have been many administrative development approaches, and each approach has its own theory, philosophy, pioneers and various field applications. The governance approach is considered one of the most important modern administrative approaches in all fields which has recently gained special importance, and has received the attention of public and private institutions, and the interest of researchers and community organizations.

In the higher education sector, university governance is a form of modern developmental reforms. It is a means to managing universities and the implementation of their strategic plans and general directions. This is done under government regulations, which are compatible with the amount of financial and human resources available, and directing university activities efficiently and effectively, with an emphasis on the quality control and continuous improvement of the academic system. Reforms in some developed countries have led to more powers to universities and they have contributed to improving its institutional performance, in its various administrative, academic, and research aspects.

Universities in the Arab region face serious challenges related to their ability to compete globally and to keep in pace with the ongoing developments in light of the fourth industrial wealth. These challenges are the result of the general trends in international/global higher education and broader societal changes, especially in recent times. Universities are functioning in an international arena that requires sound management systems in order to respond effectively to the continuously increasing demand in providing higher education and the need to maintain the quality of teaching, research and scholarship. They are also required to develop its community service and its need to develop its institutional, organizational, legal, financial, and administrative capabilities, technology, humanity, and others and to improve their positions in the international rankings.

Confronting the challenges facing education systems in Arab countries cannot be achieved through individual or regional efforts. However, huge efforts must be made at the national and regional levels to contribute to this. The efforts of the entire Arab nation, starting with politicians, decision-makers. Moreover, international experiences have proven that the real approach to development is the availability of political will among thinkers from the elite and educational leaders to various sectors of the people, including teachers, students, organizations, and social and economic activities as well as media professionals, clergy, workers, farmers...etc. So all these groups come together to formulate an Arab educational system capable of assuming the roles and responsibilities resulting from this system. This system should be capable of shaping the nation's generations and its future, and leading its social and economic development plans (Al-Khatib, 2024, p.40).

The importance of governance in higher education is increasing as it is linked to leadership. So the interest of institutions has increased the higher education through university leadership and expanding the goals of universities, such as the ability to lead colleges and departments as well as preparing students not only for the profession, but also for the profession, for society, and for life in a changing society (Singleton, 2012, p.9). In addition, most scholars and researchers today in the field of education believe that if a change is to occur in education, the beginning must be with the leadership and management of education (Behbahani, 2011, 9).

In Yemen, the government has made some efforts to reform and develop the higher and university education system in the past two decades. Among those efforts are preparation of the national strategy for higher education and scientific research, establishment of an information technology center for the higher education sector, and setting up a project to establish an education network higher education as well as proposing the competitive development project, the higher education development project, and the ministry's capacity enhancement project (UNESCO, 2009, 36). In addition, the Ministry of Higher Education made efforts in establishing academic and quality assurance of higher education. The number of public and private universities and the number of programs as well as the number of students enrolled will also increase year after year.

Given the importance of governance in educational institutions, this study comes as an attempt to identify the requirements of strengthening governance in the Yemeni and Arab higher education institutions, and offers a set of relevant useful recommendations.

Problem Statement

The problem of the study was the lack of aspects of governance in the Yemeni and Arab universities. Several recommendations of scientific conferences and relevant studies in the Arabic context have called for the necessity of adopting governance principles in higher education, including the study of Al-Sufi et al. (2020). This study concluded by confirming a project in strengthening the capabilities of higher education affiliated with the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research in Yemen, funded by the Kingdom of Netherlands to adopt the concepts of governance in higher education. It also presented a number of policies and development plans in the field of leadership, management and governance in higher education, and making them among the strategic objectives of the project. The first strategic goal was related to the management and governance of higher education, which was stated as: "The necessity of working in developing management and governance in higher education at the national and institutional levels in line with the requirements and the needs of the labor market,". This goal would be achieved at two levels: the national level and the institutional level. Each level has a number of plans, and some relevant recommendations and proposals.

Based on the above problem statement, the issue of governance in higher education is a vital research topic that has been addressed in several previous studies. These studies have identified the policies and directions necessary for good governance in higher education. It is added that the topic of governance in higher education remains a renewed research field that can be studied and analyzed, and is useful for higher educational institutions and researchers as well as an inspiration for policy makers, decision makers and relevant parties. In light of the above problem, the current study attempted to achieve the following research objectives and address the following two questions:

Research Objectives and Questions

The study aimed to achieve the following research objectives:

1. To identify the most prominent features of governance in the Yemeni higher education institutions.
2. To identify the initiatives and procedures necessary to strengthen governance in the Yemeni and Arabic higher education institutions.

To achieve these objectives, the study addressed these two research questions:

1. What are the most prominent features of governance in the Yemeni higher education institutions?
2. What are the initiatives and procedures necessary to strengthen governance in Yemeni and Arabic higher education institutions?

Significance of the Study

The importance of the current study is that it may contribute to helping leaders of higher education and leaders of universities, researchers and relevant parties to identify the reality of governance in the Yemeni and Arab universities and increase their knowledge of the requirements for its development. It may also help new researchers address issues that the current study did not address, and conduct other complementary studies on research issues that need an in-depth investigation in

addition to enriching the Yemeni and Arab library with a recent study on governance in higher educational institutions.

Definitions of Research Key Terms and Concepts

The study key terms and concepts relevant to governance in higher education are defined as follows:

Governance

Governance is defined as the method of practicing good management, and a modern tool for control. It is known as the systems, decisions and standards by which and through which the organization's work is directed and monitored at the top level for achieving justice and combating corruption (Al-Ariqi, 2017, p. 345).

Higher Education Governance

Governance in higher education is defined as a set of policies, procedures and standards for the good management of various activities carried out by universities, related to making appropriate decisions, distributing responsibilities and authorizing the necessary authorities to manage such activities based on approved rules and systems, taking into account stakeholders with integrity and transparency, aspiring to quality and excellence in performance, achieving the strategic goals of universities, and contributing to community development (Arab Universities Governance Council, 2016, p. 9).

Institutions of Higher Education

The UNESCO defines a higher education institution as an institution that provides higher education and is recognized by the competent authority or by the party in a particular state, or one of its constituent units as belonging to the higher education system (UNESCO, 2019).

Theoretical Background and Previous Studies

After extrapolating the study literature, a brief theoretical background was extracted, which is supported by a number of studies and discussed as follows:

The Origins of Governance

The need for governance has emerged in many advanced and emerging economies over the past few decades. Specifically, it emerged in the wake of the economic collapses and financial crises that many countries witnessed. The first crisis was the one that struck the countries of Southeast Asia, including Malaysia, Korea, and Japan in 1997 in addition to the recent crisis that the global economy has witnessed, especially the financial crisis in the United States of America and Europe. This recent crisis has resulted in financial difficulties among many giant companies, which almost brought them down. This has necessitated the establishment of governance rules to control the work of all stakeholders in the organization (Haider, 2019.)

Governance Concept

Governance is a modern term that began to be used increasingly at the beginning of the 1990s when the circle of those interested bodies in public issues expanded to include new actors in addition to the government, such as the media, clerics, businessmen, civil society organizations, and the army (in some societies). The influence of each component varies from one country to another depending on the

weight of the component, and in this regard, several definitions of governance have been provided and summarized by Haider (2015) from several sources as follows:

- The English term “Governance” was translated into Arabic in several meanings, the most important of which are governance, management of government affairs, administrative authority, and management of state and community affairs. However, for the present study, we used the most common term, which is governance.
- The European Union defines governance as: “actions undertaken by the executive and council’s representativeness and legality in the context of the institution (European Commission, 2001).
- As for the Asian Development Bank, it defines governance as: “the process of exercising political power and using resources institutions to manage community problems and affairs” (Asian Development Bank, 1995.) This means that governance is linked to the concept of “power,” as it is the process of making strategic institutional decisions. It also determines who exercises this power and to whom they are held accountable.

Governance of Higher Education Institutions

As stated in the Center for Research and Studies in Higher Education (2016), the governance of university institutions is also known as:

- How universities work and the methods or standards that universities follow in performing their tasks, measuring their performance, and controlling their inputs and educational processes, measuring their outputs, and harmonizing universities as a national system of higher education.
- The way universities manage their work, take their strategic decisions, and allocate their human financial resources, control and monitor their performance, methods and procedures for implementing its established regulations.
- The method through which universities are managed and the implementation of their strategic plans and general directions in light of government regulations, and compatible with the amount of financial and human resources available. It is also about directing the university activities efficiently and effectively, with an emphasis on quality control and continuous improvement for the academic system.

The Importance of Governance in Higher Education

Governance is an urgent requirement in light of the increasing crises and challenges of higher education. These challenges are represented by the number of quantitative and qualitative internal and external challenges, leading to a necessity in reconsidering the education systems and searching for alternatives that are capable of improving the effectiveness of performance. As a result, most higher education systems have changed its focus on the philosophy of quality education in restructuring their systems and educational programs (Al-Muftah, 2017, p.3).

The importance of governance of higher education institutions is represented by building trust between university and research institutions as well as productivity, and between higher education institutions and the policy-making and decision-making circles that include scientists and researchers as well as knowledge makers, who are

reliable to produce, develop and disseminate knowledge, and provide decision makers with appropriate studies, visions and perceptions regarding the issues and phenomena investigated. Moreover, there is a need to understand practitioners and public policy makers who aspire to understand how to work with researchers and scientists and researchers also look to work with makers of public policies, in addition to the parties that play the role of mediators-that is those who work in houses of practical expertise and supporting decision-making processes in the public and private sectors (Claire Karig, 2019, p.262).

The application of governance principles also aims to improve and develop the higher educational institution in all aspects: either academic or administrative. It also helps avoid intentional and unintentional errors, thus leading to publication integrity and improving the reputation of higher educational institutions (Al-Mukhniya, 2016, p.98).

Reasons for Higher Education Governance

The Association of Arab Universities quickly established the Arab Universities Governance Council, and stressed the importance of higher education governance for several reasons, the most prominent of which are stated in the Arab Universities Governance Council (2016) are presented as follows:

Establishing governance rules in the management of university affairs is an urgent matter, while leaving space for each university to build its reputation through its own performance and standards. This would advance the two systems of universities: the educational and administrative levels to better levels. Moreover, university governance needs management of changes more than the change itself. This is because many requirements do not need to be modified legal legislations, but rather to activate what exists and apply it within a policy of maximization of achievement and expanding the scope of accountability as well as monitoring the performance to proceed with the reform of university education by adopting a good method that has a realism as one of its components, and a future vision as one of its requirements.

Adopting a governance system in universities requires a clear pluralism and comprehensiveness in governance patterns. In addition, it requires a broad participation of stakeholders in strategic decisions and resource allocation as well as the presence of oversight mechanisms that enables them to deal with the executive management and direct their behavior. This is on the one hand, and on the other hand, there must be internal oversight formed by governance councils which submits reports on the extent of compliance with regulations and instructions, and the adequacy of the internal control system of the university and its efficiency.

Among the reasons for higher education governance are those relevant to the challenges of higher education. There are views presented by some researchers and those who are interested in university education (e.g., Mutahhar, 2005, p. 3-15) who pointed out at a group of challenges facing higher education, which are divided into two types: external and internal challenges, the most important of which can be summarized as follows:

First: The external challenges include globalization, communications and information technologies, and the knowledge explosion.

Second: The internal challenges include increasing social demand for higher education, high dependence on government funding, limited absorptive capacity, weak institutional capacity, weak efficiency internal affairs, limited development of

postgraduate studies, shortage of teaching staff and the need for developing professionalism and developing a culture of quality in higher education institutions.

Poor funding is one of the biggest challenges facing higher educational institutions, especially in the Arab Region which is classified as developing countries. These countries face many challenges, including financing challenges in various sectors, including the higher education and scientific research sector, which depends mainly on government funding that is quickly affected by political, security and social circumstances and economic variables. All these challenges result into negative repercussions and repercussions that affect the quality of higher education and its scientific, cognitive and research outcomes. They also limit the continuity of educational institutions in performing their assigned functions towards the society (Al-Khatib, 2024, p.34.)

Rules for Good Governance in Higher Education

Regarding the UNESCO's view of university governance, it has identified five main rules that are believed to establish together an integrated picture of good governance in institutions, including universities. These five rules are the comprehensive context, mission and objectives, management directions, independence, accountability, and participation, which are summarized as follows (Haider, 2015, p.320-321):

1. Comprehensive Context, Mission and Objectives

The context here means the university's systems, and this includes the law that regulates its work, its purpose, its regulations, its policies, administrative structure, financing, and appointments, as well as its mission and objectives. It also includes the goal of the university and how it carries out its work, and what it aims to achieve in the future.

2. Management Trends

Strong leadership and strategic planning are key components of any well-performing university. This includes administration of daily decisions and important decisions related to the operation of the university, such as admission, registration, granting certificates to students, appointing and promoting faculty and staff, and establishing facilities as well as maintaining them, securing the resources necessary for the university to carry out its mission, how to spend them, and allocating resources scarce for all claimants. It also includes the extent of the university president's authority, as well as the clarity of his/her powers in addition to the various councils and committees at the university, granting powers, and accountability procedures.

3. Independence

There is a strong international trend towards increasing the university's autonomy, with the aim of making it more responsive to its social and economic surroundings and to enable it to adapt to changes and innovations. Independence here includes academic independence (curricula, academic programs, scientific research, financial independence (total budget), institutional independence (enterprise structure), and functional independence (recruitment, salary determination, and promotion). Independence and academic freedom are important elements here.

For any university to perform well, it requires its academics' participation in the decision-making process in the university through the relevant councils and committees.

4. Accountability

Independence is usually associated with accountability. Independence cannot be granted without establishing a real accountability mechanism. Accountability means enabling university beneficiaries, individuals and groups to monitor the university's performance without leading to disruption of work or offending others.

5. Participation

Participation means providing the opportunity for beneficiaries, including individuals and civil society organizations, to participate in making university policies and in setting work rules in various areas of its activities.

Previous Related Studies

By extrapolating the literature, it appears that there are many previous studies in the field of governance, most important of which are summarized as follows:

Al-Hamzi's study (2015) aimed to identify the reality of implementing governance in the Yemeni public universities in light of the introduction to change management at Sana'a University. The study revealed a number of results, the most prominent of which are that the level of implementation of governance in the Yemeni universities as represented by Sana'a University was low. The study offered a number of recommendations, most notably: adopting and disseminating the application of governance in the Yemeni universities in light of the change management approach to all its variables. This is to enable the university to become an institutional approach that contributes to building a system of values that calls for integrity through openness at the internal and external levels of universities. The study also emphasized the necessity of having a specialized government body that is concerned with following up and practicing the principles of corporate governance. In addition, the role of senior academic and administrative leaders of the university should be activated to support the principle of administrative participation by encouraging employee participation at all levels of the management to exchange ideas, make decisions, and encourage the spirit of initiative and innovation, in addition to providing support and feedback for their suggestions towards self-actualization by enhancing their feeling of being real partners in the success and development of the university.

The study by Al-Haddabi and Al-Azizi (2019) aimed to identify the level of application of governance principles in the context of the Yemeni universities from the point of view of faculty members and academic leaders. The results showed the samples' level of appreciation of the application of governance principles was low at Sana'a University while it was high at the University of Science and Technology. As for the study by Langa and Wolhuter (2021), it indicated that there are challenges that impose on countries the governance of higher education institutions. The study indicated that universities and academics find themselves trapped between two forces: the authority and the ministry at the top level, and the students at the bottom level. In order for universities to maintain its integrity, and to fulfill its unique role in the society, this depends on two principles: the pursuit of excellence on the one hand, and preservation of its independence on the other hand.

In a study by Al-Thwaini et al. (2021), the researchers confirmed that the unemployment rate among graduates of the higher education systems in the Arab countries has constantly grown higher in the past decade. This unfortunate situation is the result of the huge margin between the skills required by the labor market and

the skills acquired by graduates of higher education. This consequently imposes the importance of university governance in the face of the present situation. The existence of effective university governance would not only contribute to the production of knowledge, but would also prepare its graduates to become useful and productive members of the local community. In addition, university governance has become a vital component that allows those responsible in institutions to mobilize resources, and make transparent decisions that lead to efficiency and effectiveness.

Hadibi's study (2021) aimed to evaluate the extent to which digitization contributes to achieving governance principles in Mohamed Boudiaf University of M'sila. The study concluded that digitization contributes to achieving the principles of governance at the University of M'sila with a positive degree, and the degree of achieving governance principles at the University of M'sila from the perspective of stakeholders represented by professors, students, and administrators was found to be high.

As for Al-Saleh's study (2020), it aimed to determine the degree of application, obstacles, and ways to enhance the principles of governance in Saudi public universities. The study concluded that the dimension of organizational effectiveness is at the forefront and justice, with a number of challenges related to the governance of Saudi public universities.

Moreover, Al-Mufaiz's study (2019) aimed to identify the reality of applying governance in Saudi universities and obstacles preventing its implementation from the point of view of university council members. The results of the study showed that the reality of applying governance areas was average. And the study sample highly agreed with the obstacles in implementing governance, including centralization, weak level of financial and administrative independence and low levels of academic freedom are the most prominent obstacles to governance in Saudi universities. In Jordan, the study by Al-Moumni (2019) aimed to identify the reality of applying governance in Jerash University from the point of view of the members of the teaching and administrative staff working there. The results showed that the implementation of governance at Jerash University reached a high degree.

As for the study by Nassif and Al-Sharji (2019), entitled: Academic Governance in Higher Education Institutions, it showed that universities are living in an era of knowledge power and the search for more efficiency, which has made management of higher education in a need of adopting modern policies to shift from the traditional model to more advanced methods development such as the governance method.

In the Sultanate of Oman, Al-Mukhainiya's study (2016) aimed to identify the requirements for applying the principles of governance in public higher education institutions in the Sultanate of Oman. The results revealed the study sample to a large extent agreed about the governance requirements. Yet, there were obstacles in applying governance, including the weak infrastructure, unclear policies, outdated regulations and laws, and officials' culture controlling the organization's culture as well as lack of follow-up to implement governance principles.

METHODOLOGY

The study relied on a descriptive analytical approach which is most appropriate to the nature of the research topic of the current study. It is one of the most widely used and appropriate methods in studying human and social phenomena as it depends on the judicious and accurate collection of a number of reliable sources of information, such

as studies, articles, and reports related to the phenomenon. The study was divided into two phases. The first phase was collecting scientific materials: printed and published on the Internet, and its number reached 25 elements which were analyzed as the study population and its sample. The second phase was analyzing the collected data and information using a content analysis method in order to extract the results necessary to answer the research questions and then provide a set of relevant recommendations and proposals relevant to governance in higher educational institutions in Yemen and the Arab Region.

Presentation of the Study Results

The answers to the research questions were divided into two dimensions: the first dimension is related to the features of governance in higher education institutions in Yemeni, and the second dimension is relevant to the initiatives and procedures necessary to enhance governance in higher education institutions in Yemeni and the Arab Region. The two dimensions are discussed as follows:

The First Dimension: The Most Prominent Features of Governance in Yemeni Higher Education Institutions

Many local studies were conducted in the Yemeni context, which have addressed the issue of governance in higher educational institutions and shed light on many aspects of governance and produced a number of important relevant results and recommendations.

One of the most important studies that addressed the issue of governance in higher educational institutions in Yemen is the study of Al-Sufi et al. (2020), and the national report submitted by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research in Yemen to the third UNESCO World Higher Education Conference on 18 - 20 May 2022 in Barcelona, Spain. This included a brief presentation on governance in higher education in Yemen, based on the analysis and evaluation of theses and dissertations related to higher education in the Republic of Yemen for the period of 1995 – 2017. As shown in Table (1), the report was based on 290 theses and dissertations of which 75 were on leadership, management and governance in higher education, thus representing (26%) compared to (71%) for quality, with a percentage of (24%).

Table (1): Studies Related to Governance in Higher Education

Domains	Number	Percentage
Management and governance	75	26%
Structure of higher education	14	5%
Quality of higher education	71	24%
Other domains	130	45%

The results of these Yemeni studies related to the management and governance of higher education as stated in (Al-Sufi et al., 2020), and (Ministry of Higher Education, 2022) revealed a number of important results that can be presented as follows:

- The Ministry of Higher Education and Yemeni universities lack an appropriate organizational culture, as a lot of money, efforts and resources that are harnessed to develop institutional work is wasted because the prevailing organizational culture does not rise to the level and scale of change and development, whether it is complete or partial.

- Weak institutional performance of higher education institutions due to imbalances in the components of the institutional performance in addition to the lack of a positive impact of strategic planning for universities.
- The weak level of efficiency in the administrative performance of the general directors of the Ministry of Higher Education, and the lack of interest on the training side, and overlapping powers between some departments within one sector.
- The Ministry of Higher Education's weak application of governance principles due to the presence of a number of obstacles despite the desire among administrative leaders to govern the ministry.
- The low degree of application of governance principles by Yemeni universities, with disparities between universities in terms of the administrative leadership, decision-making, financial and administrative review, integrity, and transparency, accountability and effective participation.
- The low level of partnership between Yemeni universities and labor market institutions, despite its importance of the future partnership between them in a number of areas such as organizational and administrative structure, and development programs and curricula, research and consulting, finance, admission policy, and instruction training, and more.
- The public higher education generally suffers from weak funding and limited governmental financial resources in exchange for increasing social demand for it, increasing needs, as well as limited funding external, weak private sector contribution, in addition to inappropriate employment of financial resources, unfair distribution of it. The sources of funding for government institutions allocated to universities come from the state budget and student fees. On the other hand, at the level of private universities, this weak financing is resulted from the weakness and limited volume of private sector investment in private higher education. They also suffer from limited investment opportunities resulting from the low incomes of most of the population. So sources of financing these private institutions are represented by the tuition fees and student fees.
- Weak private sector investment in higher education due to several reasons, including the absence of the strategic vision of both private and governmental sectors, the private sector's focus on profitable projects, administrative and financial corruption, weakness in the secure political and economic stability, and the absence of institutional work in the public and private sectors.
- Weak level of performance of university leaders due to non-compliance with the criteria for selecting leaders, the lack of training and qualification programs before and after appointments, the absence of private training centers for academic and administrative leaders, despite their desire to receive training programs and continuous rehabilitation in order to raise the level of their administrative and academic performance.
- The third function of universities, which is "community service," is still almost absent and it is obscured with ambiguity in Yemeni universities in general.

Regarding the governance of the Ministry of Higher Education in Yemen, the study by Al-Hamzi (2016) proposed a model to developing the performance of the Ministry of Higher Education and scientific research in Yemen in light of governance principles.

The study revealed a number of results, the most prominent of which are: the reality of applying governance principles in the Ministry Higher education and scientific research in Yemen have received a weak degree of application. This means that it is necessary to develop it according to the performance requirements in light of governance principles. The study also revealed that the degree of severity of obstacles reached a very high level. The study sample's estimates on the requirements for applying the governance principles reached a very high agreement. The study presented a number of recommendations, the most prominent of which are: adopting the proposed model for development of the performance of the Ministry of Higher Education in light of governance principles. It also suggests restructuring higher education in a way that suits the application of the governance principles to enable them to implement the proposed model and reconsider the legislations and the laws of higher education on the one hand, and the legislations and laws of the Ministries of Civil Service and Finance on the other hand. The study also recommends granting full powers to the Ministry of Higher Education to manage all affairs of higher educational institutions in Yemen because it represents the body responsible for higher education. It is suggested that the implementation of the process of financial and administrative accountability should be facilitated. There is a need to enhance the concept of transparency in the ministry and improve a sense of awareness among employees regarding the concept of accountability, its importance, goals, and the positives of activating it. Finally, the study suggests working to reduce the obstacles in applying the governance principles and providing its requirements.

The second dimension: Initiatives and measures necessary to enhance governance in Yemeni and Arabic higher education institutions

Based on extrapolating the relevant literature, including the Arab Universities Governance Plan (2016-2020), which was issued by the Arab universities Governance Council, in order to enhance governance in Yemeni and Arab universities, the researcher concluded the study by identifying the basic values of governance in university education, as well as the necessary procedures and initiatives to strengthen governance in Arab universities, among the main objectives, which are summarize as follows:

First: The core values of the Arab Universities Governance Council:

Values are a framework that governs the interaction between individuals inside and outside Arab universities to achieve their strategic priorities, and striving to achieve their goals as Arab universities highly value and adopt the following values (Arab Universities Governance Council, 2020, 9-10):

Governance: Governance means policies, procedures and standards for an effective management of the various activities carried out by universities. It relates to making appropriate decisions, distributing responsibilities and delegating powers necessary to manage these activities based on approved rules and systems, taking into account stakeholders with integrity and transparency in pursuit of quality and excellence in their performance, and to achieve their strategic goals and contribute to the development of the society.

Good leadership: The ability of Arab universities - whether at the individual or university level - to take actions in making conscious decisions to manage individuals or organizations, influence them to develop their performance, and support them in reaching the desired goals within terms of reference, values, and determinants in a

collective and cooperative framework. This framework should be compatible with reality and should avoid whims to develop the society according to specific strategic priorities.

Seriousness: Arab universities rely on collective and joint work to achieve the best possible achievement within the rules of well-known professional behaviors.

Commitment: Arab universities pledge to fully fulfill their collective and shared duties within the code of conduct of recognized professionalism.

Participation: Arab universities are committed to serious teamwork, positive and effective contribution, shared roles and assumed responsibilities in order to develop their performance and serve the society.

Transparency: Arab universities are committed to full disclosure and clarity in all their practices and dealings with all parties and accepting the other opinion to measure the extent of their contributions to the development of the society.

Accountability: Arab universities embrace the principle of bearing full responsibility for all their practices and activities within certified standards and full cooperation from the competent authorities.

Justice: Arab universities embrace objective standards of fairness and impartiality and ensure equal opportunities, cultural diversity and equality in rights and duties without any discrimination on the basis of race, gender or color. This is taking into account public interests.

Integrity: Arab universities adhere to the standards of ethics, justice, honesty and impartiality in issuing provisions.

Creativity: Arab universities support an atmosphere that helps their students and faculty members come up with something new or innovative and presenting something old in a new and unfamiliar way, as well as organizing ideas and showing them in a new way. They help them to solve problems or provide a real addition to the applied reality (new mental production which is useful, original, acceptable, and is able to solve a problem).

Innovation: Arab universities support an environment that helps their students and faculty members develop ideas, businesses, or designs, methods, or anything else in a better, easier, more usable, and more effective way. In other words, universities help them do something different and sophisticated to something that exists rather than improving it.

Invention: Arab universities support an atmosphere that helps their students and faculty members develop ideas or designs or methods from scratch (new and unparalleled and can be easily applied in industry).

Comprehensive quality: Arab universities are committed to continued improvement and development of their services in an integrated and comprehensive manner at all levels and setting standards for quality and excellence to match and review their performance with them. They are also committed to carrying out corrective operations in the event of any discrepancy at the appropriate time and place.

Globalization: Arab universities seek to rise to the global level through international academic accreditation for the various programs they offer, and the application of international quality standards.

Academic freedom: Arab universities are committed to encouraging freedom of thought, opinion, and scientific research, taking into account customs and traditions and respecting applicable laws.

Sustainable development: Arab universities assume their societal responsibilities and contribute to achieving sustainable development.

Second: Strategic objectives for the governance of Arab universities:

The Arab Universities Governance Council has identified three strategic objectives, which are as follows (Governance Arab universities Council, 2020, 11-14 :)

The first goal: Yemeni and Arab universities should adopt, disseminate and apply governance principles.

To achieve this goal, a set of initiatives and procedures have been identified in this regard, the most prominent of which are:

- 1) Developing a common unified Arab reference for Arab universities in the field of university governance. This is carried out by forming a governance council for Arab universities, preparing a guideline for Arabic university governance and building a list of standards (indicators) for governance and its arbitration.
- 2) Adopting and implementing governance standards in Arab universities. This should be realized by holding a conference at the university level to develop mechanisms for adopting and implementing the governance standards in Arab universities and implementing specialized workshops on the adoption and application of the standards of governance.
- 3) Encouraging Arab universities to establish governance councils, and in this regard, governance councils should be established in every university.
- 4) Spreading the culture of governance in Arab universities by forming committees to spread the culture of governance, holding workshops and brainstorming sessions and issuing and distributing governance publications.
- 5) Granting a governance certificate to universities that meet the approved standards of governance. This should be realized by forming committees that evaluate the university that wishes to obtain a governance certificate and distributing governance certificates to winning universities at the General Conference of the Association of Arab Universities.

The second goal: Building alliances between Arab universities to establish a common general framework for practicing governance

In this regard, the Arab Universities Governance Council has identified a set of procedures and initiatives, including the followings:

- 1) Exchanging administrative and scientific experiences in the field of developing university education. This can be achieved through developing programs for exchanging members of the teaching and administrative staff and conducting joint seminars and workshops.
- 2) Preparing joint field studies in the field of developing university education through conducting joint research.

- 3) Unifying university program plans while maintaining the privacy of programs according to each university. This should be realized by forming joint committees for developing common programs and standards.
- 4) Exchange of information among the Arab universities through the establishment of information centers in universities and electronic connectivity between these information centers in the Arab universities.
- 5) Developing and qualifying faculty members academically and research by holding joint training courses.
- 6) Developing effective strategies for university teaching. This can be realized by conducting joint applied research with the aim of developing university teaching strategies, holding a conference on university teaching strategies and conducting seminars and workshops on how to develop teaching strategies in the Arab universities.
- 7) Developing leadership skills among academic and administrative staff through holding special workshops on developing leadership skills.
- 8) Establishing joint research centers among the Arab universities. This can be achieved by establishing joint research centers, carrying out joint studies, allocating awards/grants for joint research among the Arab countries and involving students in joint research.
- 9) Involving faculty members in the Arab and international research networks by encouraging them to participate in the Arab and international research networks.
- 10) Developing joint research programs with Arab scientists and researchers abroad. This emphasizes the need for communicating with Arab scientists and researchers abroad.
- 11) Conducting joint research programs with Arab scientists and researchers at the university. This focuses on establishing common standards for scientific research quality through standards set by expert committees.

The third goal: Achieving sustainable development through the application of governance

These are the measures and initiatives proposed to achieve this goal:

- 1) Establishing specialized joint research centers to provide consultations to civil society institutions on sustainable development. This can be achieved through establishing advisory research centers in the field of sustainable development and conducting consulting studies and research on sustainable development.
- 2) Providing consultations to educational and training institutions through conducting consulting studies and research about education and training, training employees in the fields of education and training and creating partnerships with educational and training centers.
- 3) Providing consultations to industrial, commercial and service organizations by conducting studies and research on issues, problems and opportunities concerning the industrial, commercial and service sectors in addition to contracting seminars and workshops.

- 4) Participation in sustainable development activities in the local community by providing services to the civil society according to its needs and participating in community activities related to sustainable development.
- 5) Creating and developing joint programs among universities that meet the needs of local, regional and international communities. This should be realized through formation of joint committees from universities and civil society organizations in order to study the market needs and local, regional and international problems and opportunities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the specificity of the situation in Yemen, and the presence of many challenges at the current stage, recommendations can be made specific to the governance of the Yemeni higher educational institutions, and others are also common to the Arab universities are presented as follows:

Recommendations for the Yemeni higher education institutions

Coordination and cooperation between the Ministry, its institutions and some relevant ministries, to develop awareness among senior leaders, academics, and employees of the Ministry and universities should be made to stress the importance of organizational culture, taking into consideration that culture is an important input for facilitating changes and institutional transformation processes, which is a prominent feature age.

- Reconsidering the legislations and laws of higher education on the one hand, and the legislations and laws of the service civil and financial ministries on the other hand in order to keep pace with scientific and technical developments and political, social and economic changes at the local and regional levels.
- Restructuring higher education to suit the requirements of development and the labor market, applying the principles of governance, and developing awareness of the concept of accountability and transparency at the ministry and university levels.
- Completing the strategic planning system for the Ministry of Higher Education and universities to develop and improve the institutional performance.
- Urging and encouraging university leaders at all supervisory and executive levels to adopt values and institutional work ethics as they are more concerned than others while at the same time spreading and consolidating a positive organizational culture that is consistent with the university institution's goals and mission.
- Creating appropriate mechanisms for selecting future leaders, including academics and administrators in light of clear principles such as competition, integrity, efficiency and effectiveness, and preparing and training them on an ongoing basis.
- Creating a general climate for investment in the Yemeni public universities by providing political, social, security and economic stability.
- The necessity of commitment of the senior management of higher educational institutions to continuous training and qualification, and to benefit from the proposed programs, and establishment of special centers to train academic and administrative leaders in the Yemeni universities.

- Reconsidering the foreign scholarship policy and its mechanisms, and the policies of admission and enrollment in higher education according to clear standards, and to ensure that the country's needs for specialized personnel in various fields and areas as well as development needs and labor market are all met.
- Activating the role of oversight and accountability and eliminating extreme centralization in the decision-making process.
- Strengthening the partnership among the Yemeni public and private higher educational institutions, supporting relevant bodies, local and international organizations, which would develop the higher education and scientific research sector.
- Activating the role of senior administrative academic leaders in universities to support the principle of administrative participation. This can be achieved by encouraging the participation of employees at all management levels to exchange ideas and make decisions and encouraging the spirit of initiative and innovation.
- Raising the performance efficiency of higher education institutions, making optimal use of their available resources, filling the sources of waste, activating the evaluation of job performance, and increasing the absorptive capacity of universities and colleges in order to achieve both availability and quality.

Joint recommendations for the Yemeni and Arab higher educational institutions

To assist policy makers, decision makers, and university leaders in the Yemeni and Arab higher educational institutions, to achieve good governance in these higher education institutions, the current study found some principles, trends and policies derived from the literature review. They all focus on the rules of the UNESCO rules and the Association of Arab Universities as well as some of the leading global experiences in the field of higher education governance. They are formulated as general recommendations, which we summarize as follows:

- Developing higher education policies and strategies to ensure equal opportunities and fair distribution of services of higher education.
- Designing governance systems and councils that are diverse, comprehensive, flexible, and participatory, with monitoring mechanisms effectively and ensuring accountability and transparency by focusing on adopting state-directed governance rather than direct state governance.
- Learning from good practices of higher education governance around the world and taking into account governmental policies, institutional independence, and academic freedom.
- Diversifying the sources of funding for higher educational institutions in a way that gives sufficient flexibility to the public higher educational institutions to provide additional sources of income to implement its programs and activities.
- Adopting transformational leadership, managing changes, and establishing governance rules in administrative, financial and academic affairs.
- Reviewing university systems, their methods for selecting university leaders, and developing scientific standards that combine democracy in selection and having leadership qualities.

- Establishing leadership and governance centers in higher education and university institutions along the lines of experiments, leading global initiative, responding to the plan and recommendations of the Arab Universities Governance Council and The Arab European Leadership Network in Higher Education (ARELEN) and preparing and training qualified and specialized models in university leadership and administration.

Suggestions for future research

Future research should be conducted on the challenges of governance in higher education and the various ways to overcome these challenges in the circumstances of natural and during crises. Moreover, future studies should examine the governance requirements of the Yemeni and Arab universities in light of some contemporary experiences. Finally, it is necessary to carry out comparative studies on the level of application of governance principles in the Yemeni and Arab higher education institutions as well as in some countries of the world.

References

- 1) Al-Ariqi, M., M., I. (2017). Strategic Management - An Integrated Approach, ed 1, Al-Amin Center for Publishing and Distribution, Sana'a, Yemen.
- 2) Al-Haddabi, D., A., Y. & Al-Azizi, M., A., H (2019). The level of application of governance in the Yemeni universities: A comparative study between private and public universities. *The Arab Journal for Quality Assurance of University Education*, University of Science and Technology, 12 (39), 31-62; DOI: 10.20428/AJQAHE.12.39.2
- 3) Al-Hamzi, I., A., M. (2016). *A proposed model for developing the performance of the Ministry of Higher Education Scientific research in Yemen in light of principles of governance*. unpublished doctoral dissertation., Department of Administration Educational Planning, College of Education, Sana'a University, the National Center For information in the Republic of Yemen (14468).
- 4) Al-Hamzi, A., A., M, A, H. (2015). A proposed vision for the governance of Yemeni universities. Government in light of the introduction to change management. Doctoral dissertation, Sanaa, Yemen, the National Information Center of the Republic of Yemen (13521).
- 5) Al-Khatib, K., M. (2024). Contemporary Arab and international trends and issues in the field of higher education and scientific research, first edition, Dar Al-Dhahiria, Kuwait.
- 6) Al-Moumni, K., S. (2019): The reality of applying governance at Jerash University from the point of view Members of the teaching and administrative staff working there. *Journal of Scientific Research in Education.*, 20 (6), 501 - 523 Link: <http://search.shamaa.org/FullRecord?ID=258932>
- 7) Al-Mufaiz, K., B., A., B., M. (2019). Implementing governance in Saudi public universities: A suggested Concept. *Journal of Educational Sciences*, 15, 1439 AH - 2019 AD; university Imam Muhammad bin Saud Al-Islamiyyah, link: <http://212.138.118.109/index.php/joes/article/view/198>
- 8) Al-Muftah, H., A. (2017). Higher education and the labor market in Qatar: Reality and prospects, Arab Center for Research and Policy Studies, Qatar.
- 9) Al-Mukhainiya, Z., B., S., J. (2016). *Requirements for applying governance principles in higher educational institutions in the Sultanate of Oman*. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Department of Assets and Management Educational, College of Education, Sultan Qaboos University, Oman.
- 10) Al-Saleh, M., B., A. (2020). Principles of governance in Saudi universities: Dgree of application and ways to enhance. *Journal of Educational Sciences*, Imam Muhammad bin Saud Islamic University, 3 (23). DOI: <https://imamjournals.org/index.php/joes/article/view/1205>
- 11) Al-Sufi, M. A., H & Others. (2020). Outputs of analysis of related scientific theses in higher education in the Republic of Yemen for the period (1995-2017). First edition, sector publications Scientific research at the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, Sanaa.

- 12) Arab Universities Governance Council. (2016). The strategic plan of the Arab University Governance Council 2016 - 2020. Available at: <http://www.arabgovernance.com>
- 13) Behbahani, A. (2011). Educational Leaders and role of education on the efficiency of schools' principals. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 15, 9- 11.
- 14) Center for Research and Studies in Higher Education. (2016). Models of institutional governance systems in higher education in the United States of America. A scientific publication entitled: Selected Readings in University Education, Issue (60), Jumada al-Akhir - 1436 AH, issued by the Research Center Studies in higher education, Saudi Arabia.
- 15) Claire, C. (2019). How does government listen to scientists? *Review of Hakama Magazine*, 2- 261-263.
- 16) Hadibi, S. (2021). *The contribution of digitization to achieving governance principles in Algerian universities*. Doctoral dissertation, University of M'sila, DOI: <http://dspace.univ-msila.dz:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/26357>
- 17) Haider, A., L., H. (2015). Restructuring higher education - from higher education to higher education. Sana'a, Republic of Yemen.
- 18) Haider, A., L., H. (2019). The training program for faculty members in Yemeni universities, entitled: Governance of Higher Education Institutions and Improving Education, sponsored by the Ministry Higher Education and the German Agency for International Cooperation GIZ, 18 - 20 November 2019, Sana'a, Yemen.
- 19) Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research (2022). National report submitted by the Ministry of Education Higher education and scientific research in Yemen for the Third UNESCO World Conference on Higher Education, May 18-20 2022 AD - Barcelona - Spain, Edited by: Dr. Khalil Al-Khatib, Sanaa, Yemen.
- 20) Mutahhar, M., M. (2005). Challenges facing higher education in the Republic of Yemen: Reality and future vision. National Information Center, Presidency of the Republic, Yemen.
- 21) Nassif, M., & Al-Sharji, A., S. (2019). Academic Governance in higher educational institutions. *Journal of Educational Roots and Social Sciences*, 6 (6), 359-382.
- 22) Singleton, M., K. (2012). *A Design, Implementation, and Evaluation of Peirce College Student Leadership Development Program*. Doctorate dissertation of Education in Innovation and Leadership. Wilmington University. UMI Dissertation publishing by ProQuest. UMI No: 3493826.
- 23) UNESCO. (2009). UNESCO regional report on the Arab Regional Conference on Education Entitled: Achievements of higher education in Arab countries and its challenges, towards an Arab space for education Higher: Global challenges and societal responsibilities, for the period May 31 to June 2, 2009 Cairo. UNESCO Regional Office for Education in the Arab States, Beirut.
- 24) UNESCO. (2019). Global Convention on the Recognition of Qualifications for Higher Education, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, Education Sector, viewed on: 7-8-2023, Available at: <file:///C:/Users/MC/Downloads/372970ara.pdf>
- 25) Wolhuter C. and Langa P. (2021). Management and Governance in Higher Education: South African Universities under Siege", *Acta Paedagogica Vilnensia*, 46,105-118. DOI:10.15388/ActPaed.2021.46.7